

FOR THE MEMORY OF PROFESSOR ATAXANOV

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ABSTRACT

Teaching others, enriching knowledge is an admirable action. The level of individuals entrusted with such responsible tasks is really significant. Indeed, knowledge does not arise spontaneously in individuals. Teacher is needed for this. Teaching and being teacher are as great as knowledge and demanding it. Teachers and mentors educate such skilled young professionals. One of the great jobs among thousands of jobs in the world is teaching.

Introduction: Ergash Isabaevich Ataxanov (1914 – 1967) – soviet scientist and educator, biophysicist, therapist, doctor of medical sciences, professor, member of the Academy of Medical Sciences of the Uzbek SSR (1960), associate member of the Academy of Medical Sciences of USSR (1960, 1961) was born on September 10, 1914 in Namangan. He studied at Tashkent Medical Institute from 1931 to 1936. He studied at the postgraduate course of the same institute between 1936 – 1941. From 1941 to 1967, he worked as a teacher at the Tashkent Medical Institute, from 1943 to 1949 as an associate professor, from 1949 to 1951 as a professor at the hospital therapeutic polyclinic, and from 1951 to 1967 as the head of the department of internal diseases **propedeutics**. From 1955 to 1962, he was also engaged in scientific activities as the chairman of the Scientific Council of the Ministry of Health of the Uzbek SSR.

Methodology: Main academic and **pedagogical** activity was connected with **hematology**, regional pathology, and problems of the pathology of organs of digestion. Under his leadership, the study of liver pathology and metabolic processes in hot climate was conducted, changes in **hematopoietic** system in health problems related to digestion were demonstrated, and the mechanisms of pathogenesis of malignant anemia, **erythremia** and **leukemia** were systemized.

Results: E.I. Ataxanov was one of the pioneers in the Soviet Union in the treatment of internal organ diseases with **oxyl** hydrolysates and the use of lipotropic agents in the treatment of chronic hepatitis. He defended his doctoral dissertation on the topic "Materials on the pathogenesis and clinic of various forms of anemia," in 1941 and on the topic "Basic materials on anemia" in 1948 in order to get the academic title of candidate of medial subjects. He was elected as an associate member of the Academy of Medical Sciences of the USSR. Under the leadership of E.I. Ataxanov, significant scientific works, including monographs, were carried out. Ataxanov passed away on May 11, 1967 in Tashkent.

Discussion: Ergash Isabaevich Ataxanov is a prominent educator who has raised our youth with love for the motherland, loyalty, respect for national traditions and values, and has successfully pursued a righteous and fruitful career in the teaching profession. The high awards of our country are also a confirmation of this achievement. We, the youth, should follow in the footsteps of our teachers, making appropriate efforts to grasp the peaks of knowledge.

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